

Research on Dynamic Multi-Object Recognition based on Machine Vision

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Abstract: Dynamic multi-object recognition based on machine vision is a very important research direction in the field of pattern recognition. In this paper, the multi-object identification of robotic fishes in water is studied and A HSV color space model is proposed. By re-modeling the original color space, the main light interference in the image can be effectively removed, and the shadow of the robotic fish can be removed, making the background segmentation more accurate. The improved algorithm has stronger robustness than the original matching tracking algorithm

Keywords: *Robotic fish, target recognition, machine vision, HSV, deep learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

Target tracking has become an important research direction and research hot spot in the field of computer vision [1]. After years of development, the target tracking technology has made great progress, but it still faces many challenges, such as changes in light, drift caused by occlusion, and even tracking failure. The current target tracking algorithm performs target recognition by extracting the external features of the tracking object. Then, the matching similarity between the candidate object and the template in the frame images is calculated to determine the position of the object so as to achieve tracking of the object. This method includes two parts: target recognition and target matching. This paper proposes a color space model algorithm based on HSV [2]. After remodeling the original color space, we effectively remove the main light interference in the image and the shadow interference of the robotic fish [3], making the image segmentation and recognition of multiple robotic fishes are more accurate, so the improvement of the algorithm makes the original matching tracking algorithm more robust

II. TEMPLATE MATCHING

Template matching is one of the important components

of digital image processing. The method of spatially aligning two or more images captured by different sensors or the same sensor at the same time under different imaging conditions for the same scene, or finding a corresponding pattern according to a known pattern to another image is called Template matching.

For a specific experimental environment, that is, the blue pool as a background, modeling, and the original platform uses a method of extracting foreground information in a static background, and the image is applied to follow-up template matching tracking.

In the experimental platform, RGB channel modeling is used, because the background color is mainly blue, so the coefficient is adjusted to 1:2:7 according to the Lagrange multiplier algorithm to make a better distinction between foreground and background. First select the static background without fish, save it as a static background image, Influenced by the reflection and shadow of the water surface, it is necessary to set the threshold value on the edge averaging method after the background is made poor, and filter out these interference points by means of median filtering. Then use the template matching algorithm to match the previously designed oval template with the extracted fish. Utilize the basic means of human eye recognition to make fuzzy positioning for the robotic fish in the

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water within the video camera recording range [4]. Then the position of the robot fish in the water is transmitted to the computer, and the location and attitude of the fish in the water are identified by the fuzzy framework [5].

In order to let the match results more accurate, template matching algorithm using the double templates. The foreground template matches the white part and the background part matches the black part, so the matching is faster and more robust [6].

Fig 1. Double layer formwork

However, in the actual competition, it was found that the swimming pool module was not perfect, the environment was changeable, the reflection of the pool, and some environmental factors seriously affected the tracking effect [7]. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the large platform algorithm. The disadvantages of the model construction of the machine fish pool are as follows.

- A. The lighting effects of the pool, such as uneven lighting, the edge of the pool obstructed the light, resulting in the background of the previous collection is invalid;
- B. The shadow of the fish affects the target mark
- C. The color of the robot fish is seriously distorted when the target acquisition is carried out in the irregular reflective area caused by the shaking of the water surface.
- D. The recognition and tracking effect of this model is not suitable for colored fishes.

III. ALGORITHM IMPROVEMENT

3.1 Algorithm Introduction

In order to reduce the influence of light and fish shadow

and to recognize the color fish effectively, a better classification algorithm based on HSV feature space is introduced in this paper.

Compared with RGB channel, HSV is closer to the human eye perception of color, the color properties of H is an accurate reflection of the kinds of color, with a relatively low sensitivity to changes in the environment, very suitable for image processing [8].

First of all, we need to analyze how these different colors of fish, ponds, and backlights are distributed in the HSV space so that we can do classification processing later. Data extraction steps are as follows:

- A. Manually select 20*20 pixels wide area as candidate target.
- B. Load the selected image and select the area as much as possible for the machine fish or the center point of the object to be divided.
- C. All these points are stored in HSV 3d space, and then 3d images are drawn through Matplotlib. These values are collected and arranged, and the actual colors are distributed as follows:

Table I.HSV spatial numerical distribution

	black	gray	White	red	
H (min)	0	0	0	0	155
H (max)	180	180	180	11	180
S (min)	0	0	0	43	
S (max)	255	43	30	255	
V (min)	0	46	221	46	
V (max)	46	220	255	255	

Table II .continued

	OR	YLV	GR N	BL U	VLT
H (min)	11	26	35	100	125
H (max)	25	34	77	124	155
S (min)	43	43	43	43	34
S (max)	255	255	255	255	255
V (min)	46	46	46	46	46
V (max)	255	255	255	255	255

Data analysis:

As a result of the laboratory pool is made of glass,

relative to the competition pool, reflective more serious. In the sunlight, the pool color is distributed between blue and blue. We will adjust the color of this range to 0, that is, the background black.

There is also a problem that needs to be solved. There is a part of the red distribution in the 0-10, and 156-180, which will affect the recognition of the red Koi fish, which can make a part of the foreground map of the fish is darkened and part of it is white, we need to adjust this part show black red to highlight range, while the prospect of black fish need other ways to deal with.

3.2 Improvement of Experimental Parameters

So when we adjust the color to the highlighted part, we adjust the color of the background and lighting to zero. You can see the effect as follows: we still can't see the black fish.

Fig.2 Parameter adjustment of H channel

VSRB color channel

Fig.3 Other color channel testing

In figure 3, we can find that the B channel and V channel can be used in these diagrams, because the black fish can be extracted clearly, and the influence of light, pool background and other factors is very small.

3.3 Algorithm Tray and Improvement

We try to integrate these channels and the reclassified H channel, and the results are as follows: At this time, the fish image is clear, but there are still some water wave impurities. So the median filter is used to filter the image.

Fig.4 Dual channel fusion

IV. TESTING

4.1 Testing in Different Environment

Compared to the previous prospect extraction method, the present method is more simple, complex algorithm is low, also do not need to collect background and open the camera to choose fish for competition, easy to operate, solved all the problems caused by the previous environment, so it is integrated into the global robotic fish platform to further test results in various universities.

Fig.5 Guangxi university of science and technology testing

From the test results of Guangxi University of science and technology, we can see that even the yellow fish can't be seen by the human eye, and the computer can tell the part of the fish.

Fig.6 China University of Geosciences testing

You can see that the fish and the ball in the pool have a good segmentation effect.

Fig.7 Beijing university glass pool testing

The video, which is recorded to different environments, can be seen that the red fish and yellow fish are extracted, and the light is turned into a black background.

Fig.8 Beijing University of Technology testing

4.2 Different Light Interference Testing

4.2.1 Strong Light Testing

Fig.9 Beijing university pool strong light testing

Fig.9 B In the laboratory we add the maximum amount of light interference. Part of the fish is rendered white, Video is processed without changing any parameters, and it can be found that the method is still effective in extracting the contour of the fish.

4.2.2 Weak Light Testing

Fig.10 Beijing university pool weak light testing

It can be seen that the fish can still be extracted without any internal light source. Through testing, the algorithm is very effective and can replace the foreground extraction algorithm.

V. CONCLUSION

After remodeling the original color space, it effectively reduces the illumination in the image and the influence of the shadow of the robotic fish, making the segmentation and tracking of robotic fish is more accurate. Due to the improvement of the algorithm, the original matching tracking algorithm is more robust. The disadvantage is that this method only applies to the background pure environment and the machine fish collision cannot make a good distinction, and further research will be conducted to solve this problem.

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